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THE CREATION OF A SERVICE CLUSTER AND ITS SELF-REGULATION CONTRIBUTE TO THE DEVELOPMENT OF AN INNOVATIVE INFRASTRUCTURE

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Annotation: In this article, an important feature that distinguishes a small financial cluster from others is the commonality of models of production, cooperative and other interaction of business entities, a clearly expressed leadership factor. Therefore, an important aspect that distinguishes the cluster is the factor of innovation orientation of the participants of the small financial cluster. Clusters, as a rule, are formed where progressive growth in the field of production technologies and equipment is expected or underway and reaching new "market positions" in the future.

Keywords: Small financial enterprises, cluster, innovation, infrastructure, innovation infrastructure, innovation activity, competitiveness, financial services.

Introduction

The problem of clustering the production of small financial enterprises in the country is of particular relevance due to the technological modernization of all sectors of the national economy. In this regard, the country focuses on creating the

necessary institutional environment that will increase the opportunities for innovative development of small financial enterprises of all forms of ownership (services, processing enterprises, small businesses and private entrepreneurship, etc) Therefore, increasing the competitive activity of small financial enterprises should be aimed at finding new forms of combining production factors, creating new products, and developing markets

Review of literature on the topic.

M. Porter believes that it is appropriate to view a country's competitiveness not through individual firms, but through the international competitiveness of clusters - associations of firms in different industries. In particular, it is believed that the ability of these clusters to effectively utilize internal resources is of great importance.

The cluster approach to studying economic processes in determining competitiveness is also used in a number of other theories:[1]

E.Leumer identified clusters with high export levels in the national level of agricultural production; [2]

I. Tolenado and D. Solier used the concept of "filers" to define groups of technological fields; [3]

E. Dahmen's cluster theory is based on his thesis "on development blocks";[4]

The advantage of the theory developed by V. Feldman is that it is based on a large-scale empirical study of diversified enterprises in different countries.[5]

In his dissertation on the topic "Development of innovative infrastructure in agro-industrial production in the context of modernization of the national economy," B.O. Dusmatov emphasized that, in accordance with world practice, the following are the main characteristics of clusters in small financial enterprises.[6]

Analysis and results

According to global practice, the following are the main characteristics of clusters in small financial services enterprises:the existence of systematic agreements, cooperation and cooperation (including state-partnership agreements, mutual

agreements) among the cluster participants; the stability of economic relations between economic entities - cluster participants, the fact that these relations have a predominant importance for the majority of cluster participants;

High innovative activity of cluster participants, focus on continuous improvement of competitive advantages (regional universities and institutes, scientific centers, innovation centers, etc.);

the presence of a leading, large organization that determines the long-term economic, innovative and other strategies of the entire system (for a financial cluster - a financial services company, etc.);

Long-term coordination of interactions between cluster participants within the framework of programs, innovative activities, basic management systems, quality control, etc.

The innovative orientation of the participants of the small financial services cluster is an important feature that distinguishes the cluster. Clusters are typically formed in areas where advanced growth in technology and engineering is expected or is occurring and where future entry into new "market niches" is anticipated.

The goal of the state cluster policy is to create conditions for increasing the competitiveness of the economy of a complex of small financial service enterprises through the introduction of a cluster model of development. In line with this goal, the following objectives of the public service cluster policy should be established:

It is necessary to improve the existing regulatory documents regulating the development of service clusters, including the development of a separate Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Cooperation of Small Financial Service Enterprises" and the inclusion in it of forms of cooperation of small financial service enterprises. The Republic of Uzbekistan should develop a new draft law "On Clusters and Cluster Activities" that fully and clearly covers possible types of clusters, including service clusters, the tasks and objectives of their organization, their rights, obligations, the rights of members, and similar issues;

determining priority areas for the formation and development of service clusters;
creating conditions for professional training of specialists and managers in the development of service clusters;

Creating conditions for the development and implementation of service cluster initiatives and projects;

It is necessary to plan the formation of cluster initiatives in small financial services enterprises, as well as small businesses and private entrepreneurs interested in the future implementation of cluster projects.

Organize information and explanatory work on the prospects for using the cluster model for the development of small financial service enterprises. This requires holding information and educational events for government agencies and representatives of the business community on cluster development issues with the participation of foreign experts, including the study of practical experience in initiating and implementing specific cluster projects.

Currently, it is advisable to ensure the formation of service clusters in two organizational forms:

Services are coordinated between cluster participants in a number of areas (conducting marketing research, organizing and conducting joint research and development work and innovative projects, implementing information, educational and advertising activities, organizing the construction and operation of public facilities, etc.) in the interests of all cluster participants

Conclusion of a simple cooperation agreement (joint activity agreement) under which the activity will be carried out. In this case, a cluster council will be formed from the leaders of the participants, but a special apparatus that will perform the functions of a cluster development center will not be established;

Service cluster participants may establish a separate legal entity (limited liability company) in addition to the cluster council, or transfer functions to an existing organization that is considered a cluster development organization. A cluster

development organization may be established in the form of an agroholding company.

Another important feature that distinguishes service clusters from others is the commonality of models of cooperation and other interactions of economic entities, namely, a clearly expressed factor of the leading (integrating) product.

Local governments interact with service cluster structures even in the absence of a clear cluster approach. The use of clustering mechanisms allows for the effective structuring and coordination of state funding in the area of new knowledge and product creation. In addition to the implementation and coordination of state support mechanisms, government bodies serve the active process of cluster development by ensuring the legitimacy of the activities of cluster development centers and providing financial support.

Conclusions and suggestions

In summary, an algorithm for generating strong small molecular clusters was proposed, based on the above-mentioned ones:

In creating a service cluster, the formation of synergistic effects as a result of the creation of the entire technological chain, from initial service to the consolidated sale of services, is of particular importance, which, in turn, will lead to an increase in the innovative attractiveness of the industry. The implementation of cluster policy in the Uzbek economy will help increase the competitiveness of enterprises through effective cooperation between cluster participants, access to innovations, technologies, know-how, specialized services, highly qualified personnel, and other opportunities. The duration of the stages of formation of service clusters depends on the availability of multilateral resources, the level of interest of the main participants, and the level of development of the institutional environment. Based on the above, the following algorithm for identifying strong service clusters is proposed:

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